

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS: KEY ASPECTS AND CHALLENGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10201332>

Abstract. *The article discusses management, human resource management in educational institutions, its main aspects and problems.*

Keywords: *management, resource, recruiting, development, adaptation, motivation, organization, correction.*

Management is the process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling the resources (including people, finance, technology, and other resources) of an organization to achieve specified goals or objectives. Management involves coordinating and directing the activities of an organization or part of it to ensure optimal use of resources to achieve desired results.

Basic controls include:

Planning: Defining goals, developing strategies and plans that determine the direction of the organization.

Organization: Creation of an optimal structure and distribution of tasks and responsibilities among employees of the organization to achieve set goals.

Direction (Leadership): Motivating and guiding employees in completing tasks, ensuring their effectiveness and productivity.

Control: Evaluating and monitoring the implementation of plans and achievement of goals, adjusting activities if necessary to improve results.

Management can be applied in a variety of contexts, including business organizations, government agencies, non-profit organizations, and other entities. In the modern world, management is also associated with the use of modern information technologies, data analytics and other innovative methods to optimize business processes and make informed decisions. Management is a key element of the successful functioning of any organization, helping to achieve strategic goals and ensuring sustainability and growth.

“Personnel management”, which includes several control blocks. Let's give them a brief description.

Personnel adaptation management is a subprocess of adaptation to the content and conditions of organizational culture and the immediate social environment of the organization for effective performance and adequate behavior.

Personnel movement management is a sub-process of moving employees within an organization and includes promotion, demotion, transfer to another position, dismissal, etc.

Management of training and retraining of employees is a sub-process carried out in order to obtain professional skills and abilities to perform specific job responsibilities. Provides different levels of training.

Managing the assessment of specialists is a sub-process carried out to determine the suitability of an employee for a vacant or occupied workplace (position) based on his individual contribution to the organization's activities, personal qualities and the dynamics of professional development.

Managing the qualifications of specialists is a sub-process of purposefully increasing the professional competence of specialists to perform tasks of a higher level.

Recruitment management is a sub-process of attracting candidates for positions who meet the necessary requirements for occupying vacant jobs, as well as determining compliance with the type of activity and making a decision on the suitability or unsuitability of candidates for the position.

Personnel demand management is a sub-process of determining the availability of vacancies that need to be filled in accordance with the main parameters (quantity, quality, time of acceptance), as well as the required characteristics of the specialist.

Personnel placement management is a sub-process of distributing (and redistributing) workers to jobs (positions) on the basis of scientifically based standards of labor costs, as well as in compliance with the proportions determined for given conditions by qualifications, social activity, age, gender, taking into account the compatibility of employees.

Management of a reserve of managers is a sub-process of identifying some of the organization's specialists who have the appropriate potential to occupy higher management positions in the future.

Career management for managers is a subprocess of determining the individually conscious position of some specialists and supporting it for consistent advancement up the career ladder in the organization.

Managing the development of specialists is a sub-process of improving the personal qualities of specialists, which contribute to increasing the potential of the organization's specialists.

Personnel documentation management is a sub-process of systematic registration, maintenance, storage and issuance of personnel documents for each individual employee of the organization. Currently, many organizations maintain a personnel database using software.

Managing certification of specialists is a sub-process the means by which a third party certifies in writing that a specific employee of an organization meets certain qualification requirements for a specific profession.

Managing wages and employee benefits is a sub-process of determining the level of remuneration for the corresponding position and social benefits for various categories of personnel, as well as changing them in accordance with various factors (inflation, professionalism, movement up the career ladder).

Managing the potential of specialists is a sub-process of determining determining the employee's future capabilities based on recording changes in his various professional and personal qualities over a certain period of time.

Human resource management can be viewed as the development of formal systems in an organization to ensure that human talent is used effectively and efficiently to achieve organizational goals. Griffin defined human resource management as a set of organizational activities aimed at attracting, developing and maintaining effective personnel [4]. Human resource management deals with purchasing or hiring, staffing, welfare, maintenance, training and retraining, placement, promotion, motivational relations, compensation or reward, transfer and discipline of personnel. It's all about the efficiency of the organization. Human resource management is a fundamental management function that determines the performance of personnel in any organization. This simple statement implies that when staff in education systems are

properly recruited, selected and supervised, inducted and rewarded appropriately, supported, developed, appraised and promoted, they will be committed to their work. will remain dedicated and productive in their work. education systems. We can simply say that this is the coordination of the activities and efforts of employees of an educational organization to achieve educational goals. Therefore, human resource management in education is the process of motivating employees to maximize their productivity in order to obtain maximum output, starting from the day they are hired. This means using people to perform duties and functions in education. Human resources are easily recognized as the most important resource needed to produce goods and services. Human resources are the key to rapid socio-economic development and efficient service delivery.

Human resource management in educational organizations is an important and complex process that affects the quality of education, professional development of teaching staff and student success. Effective human resource management is necessary to create a supportive learning environment that promotes the growth of students' knowledge and skills. This article examines the key aspects and challenges that educational organizations face when managing their human resources.

1. Recruiting and hiring staff

One of the primary aspects of human resource management in educational institutions is the correct selection of qualified personnel. The recruiting and hiring process requires careful planning and assessment of the school's needs to find educators who meet the educational standards and values of the organization.

2. Professional development and training

Educational organizations must invest in the professional development of their teaching staff. This includes learning new teaching methods, using modern educational technologies and developing soft skills such as communication and leadership. Continuous training allows teachers to keep abreast of the latest trends in education and enrich their lesson material.

3. Performance management

Assessing and managing the performance of teaching staff is a key aspect of human resource management. Effective assessment methods, feedback and incentives to improve the quality of education contribute to the growth of professionalism of teachers and, as a result, to an increase in the educational level of students.

4. Development of corporate culture

Creating a positive corporate culture in an educational organization helps improve the working atmosphere, increases the level of employee motivation and strengthens relationships within the team. Developing shared values, ethical principles and standards of behavior helps create a cohesive and harmonious educational environment.

5. Opportunities and challenges of technology implementation

Modern educational technologies play an important role in teaching and managing the educational process. However, technology integration requires investment in equipment, staff training, and data security. The introduction of technology also implies the need to constantly update the knowledge and skills of teaching staff.

6. Adaptation to changes in the educational sphere

The educational environment is constantly changing under the influence of new educational standards, legislative changes and sociocultural trends. Human resource management

in educational organizations requires flexibility and the ability to adapt to change, respond to new requirements and innovations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, from what has been analyzed and discussed above arguments it can be inferred as follows that human resource management in educational organizations presents many complex aspects that impact educational quality and student success. To successfully address challenges in this area, continuous training, development of effective strategies and consideration of the characteristics of each specific educational organization are necessary. Understanding the importance of human resource management helps create an educational environment that promotes the development of all participants in the educational process and the formation of a successful future for each student.

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